

SCANNING AND SKIMMING AS AN IMPORTANT TYPE OF READING SKILL

Fayzrakhmanova Zarina Ildarovna

Branch of the Federal state budget educational institution of higher education
"National research university "MPEI" In Tashkent Department of Natural, Technical
and Social Sciences and Humanities English teacher

ABSTRACT: *Scanning is reading rapidly in order to find specific facts. While skimming tells you what general information is within a section, scanning helps you locate a particular fact. Scanning refers to looking through a text very quickly to find specific details. For example, when we are searching for a telephone number in a directory, we scan the page for the name of the specific person we are looking for. This article is devoted to the scanning as an important type of reading skill*

KEY WORDS: *skimming, scanning, intensive reading, extensive reading, discourse, skills.*

INTRODUCTION

Learning a discipline involves developing familiarity with the ways of being, thinking, writing, and seeing the world of those experts in the discipline. Reading academic texts published by those disciplinary experts permits students to immerse in the culture of the discipline and facilitates learning its conventions, discourse, skills, and knowledge.

But, this is only possible if students take a deep approach to reading. A surface approach to reading is the tacit acceptance of information contained in the text. Students taking a surface approach to reading usually consider this information as isolated and unlinked facts. This leads to superficial retention of material for examinations and does not promote understanding or long-term retention of knowledge and information. In contrast, a deep approach to reading is an approach where the reader uses higher-order cognitive skills such as the ability to analyze, synthesize, solve problems, and thinks meta-cognitively in order to negotiate meanings with the author and to construct new meaning from the text.

METHODS

RESULTS AND ANALYSES

The four main types of reading techniques are the following: **1. Skimming; 2. Scanning; 3. Intensive reading; 4. Extensive reading**

Skimming is sometimes referred to as gist reading. Skimming may help in order to know what the text is about at its most basic level. You might typically do this with

a magazine or newspaper and would help you mentally and quickly shortlist those articles which you might consider for a deeper read. You might typically skim to search for a name in a telephone directory.

Scanning may be imagined like this, picture yourself visiting a historical city, guide book in hand. You would most probably just scan the guide book to see which site you might want to visit.

In intensive reading you need to have your aims clear in mind when undertaking intensive reading. Remember this is going to be far more time consuming than scanning or skimming. If you need to list the chronology of events in a long passage, you will need to read it intensively.

Extensive reading involves reading for pleasure. Because there is an element of enjoyment in extensive reading it is unlikely that students will undertake extensive reading of a text they do not like.

Reading comprehension is not just a receptive process, it implies a complex process in which the readers identify basic information and are able to predict, to infer, to argue and to recognize writers points of view.

Before reading or pre-reading activities are a crucial and often-neglected step in the reading process. Preparing students to read can build their interest, confidence, and motivation for reading the text and can facilitate comprehension when the text is later closely read.

DISCUSSION

First Reading could be argued that a first reading is part of the pre-reading stage, but we discuss it here to distinguish clearly between the stages of preparing to read the text and actually reading it.

During Reading stands after pre-reading. Although reading textbooks and teachers have for decades included post-reading comprehension, discussion, and writing activities as key instructional components, it is only over the past two decades or so that reading specialists have focused more intentionally on what students do (or should do) during reading.

After reading students have read a text several times for main ideas, have comprehended its essential content, and have spent time considering the text's language and structure, the final stage of intensive reading is to help students evaluate and extend what they have learned about the text and the reading process. *Scanning* involves running your eyes down the page looking for specific facts or key words and phrases. Similarly, scanning skills are valuable for several purposes in studying science. First, they are an aid in locating new terms, which are introduced in the chapter. Unless you understand the new terms, it is impossible to follow the author's reasoning without a dictionary or glossary. Thus, a preliminary scanning of the chapters will alert you to the new terms and concepts and their sequence. When you locate a new term, try to find its definition. If you are not able to figure out the meaning, then

look it up in the glossary or dictionary. (Note: usually new terms are defined as they are introduced in science texts. If your text does not have a glossary, it is a good idea to keep a glossary of your own in the front page of the book. Record the terms and their definition or the page number where the definition is located. This is an excellent aid to refer to when you are reviewing for an examination, as it provides a convenient outline of the course). [1, 13]

Secondly, scanning is useful in locating statements, definitions, formulas, etc. which you must remember completely and precisely. Scan to find the exact and complete statement of a chemical law, the formula of a particular compound in chemistry, or the stages of cell division. Also, scan the charts and figures, for they usually summarize in graphic form the major ideas and facts of the chapter. If you practice these skimming and scanning techniques prior to reading a science chapter, you will find that not only will your intensive reading take much less time, but that your retention of the important course details will greatly improve.

Because you already scan many different types of material in your daily life, learning more details about scanning will be easy. Establishing your purpose, locating the appropriate material, and knowing how the information is structured before you start scanning is essential. The material you scan is typically arranged in the following ways: alphabetically, chronologically, non-alphabetically, by category, or textually. **Alphabetical** information is arranged in order from A to Z, while **chronological** information is arranged in time or numerical order.

In the past, you probably scanned without knowing you were doing it. Now with the information provided in this section, you can use scanning more intentionally and frequently. The more you practice, the more effective scanning will become. Finally, the most important benefit of scanning is its ability to help you become a more flexible reader. Scanning adds another high gear to your reading.

Previewing key sentences can be found at the very beginning of a paragraph or chapter. The first few sentences will give you a good idea about the paragraph.

Each paragraph usually delivers one idea, though paragraphs may often relate to each other. Once you understand the central idea behind each paragraph block you will quickly get the gist of it. This may aid you in understanding the whole chapter a lot faster.

You can also use a different approach – just look for the applicable information that you require and skip the rest. Another tactic is to read the first and the last sentence of longer paragraphs which may give you a more relevant summary and to pick up the central idea.

Scan for name and numbers are present in every text and they narrate to details about people, places and concepts. There is no order of getting those information in a text during previewing. One of the best ways of scanning for this sort of information is to move your finger or pointer across the page (you can use serpentine style or zigzag)

you will notice that you will quickly remember a number or a few names. After that just read the whole text so that you can get a complete picture.

Scanning trigger words are to preview a text while keeping a lookout for important key words and if wanted to jot them down. Mainly you will spot nouns or compounds. Trigger words usually include numbers, names, places and key sentences. You will need to practice this yourself to see what works for you, but the skill of scanning includes: 1. The skill of reading right to left and up and down: that way your brain can't slow you down by trying to understand the text. 2. The skill of starting in the middle: you are more likely to find word quickly that way.

Most people use scanning to read web pages when surfing the internet. Scanning helps you establish where in a book or article specific information is located.

As a conclusion we can say that Reading is one of the key language skills that students should acquire in the process of learning a foreign language. Moreover, it is not only the goal of education but also a means of learning a foreign language as while reading students review sounds and letters, vocabulary and grammar, memorize the spelling of words, the meaning of words and word combinations i.e. they polish their foreign language knowledge. To make teaching reading effective it is advisable to focus on one skill at a time, explain the purpose of given tasks, establish connection with the previously acquired knowledge and skills, make usage of visual and audio aids, discuss problematic issues etc. Teachers should also keep in mind that reading is not a passive skill, make students engaged with what they are reading, encouraged them to respond to the content of a reading text not just to the language, to make sure that tasks correspond to the topic and level of the students etc.

CONCLUSION

All the things considered, reading is a language activity and ought not to be divorced from other language activities. To read effectively in English students need to learn to think in English. The methods of any teaching reading lesson should be chosen according to the learner's level of skill development. Teaching reading is a job for an expert who has to create conditions whereby learners can learn and develop their reading skills. Understand a reading text properly and be able to work with it effectively is a skill that needs time to be mastered. This is the reason for starting teaching reading comprehension to young learners and use children's literature during this process.

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